

Simulation of various types of faults in VVER-1200 using PCTTRAN

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Abstract

An essential component of a nuclear power plant (NPP) that generates energy is the nuclear reactor. There are many different kinds of reactors around the globe. The VVER-1200 reactor is a Generation III+ reactor and is regarded as one of the safest reactors in the world, but there is always a chance of faults. Nuclear reactor safety analysis is critical for understanding reactor behavior. This study utilizes the PCTTRAN VVER-1200 simulation software to model transient responses under multiple fault scenarios, including Loss of Coolant Accident (LOCA), partial Loss of AC Power (60%), Steam Generator Tube Rupture (30% in Generator A, 45% in Generator B), and Auxiliary Pump Malfunction. The simulation begins at full power operation (100%) with steady-state conditions before faults are introduced at $T = 5s$. The results indicate that LOCA leads to a rapid loss of coolant, triggering a sharp rise in peak fuel temperature and cladding temperature, followed by emergency cooling system activation to stabilize conditions. The departure from nucleate boiling ratio (DNBR) initially drops but subsequently recovers as cooling is restored. The transient response also shows a rapid decline in reactor core thermal power, nuclear flux, and turbine load, highlighting the reactor's automatic shutdown (SCRAM) mechanism. These findings emphasize the importance of passive and active safety systems in mitigating severe accident scenarios in VVER-1200 reactors.

Keywords— nuclear power plant, PCTTRAN, VVER-1200, NPP fault.

1. INTRODUCTION

A nuclear reactor is an arrangement where a self-sustained nuclear chain reaction is initiated and controlled. In a nuclear power plant, they are used in electricity generation. According to the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) early report in 2019, there are around 451 active nuclear power reactors and 226 research reactors in operation around the world [1]. Among them, VVER-1200 reactors are considered as one of the most advanced on design and efficiency. VVER-1200 is the latest version of VVER reactors. VVER stands for Vodo-Vodyanoi Energetichesky Reaktor, which means water water energetic reactor in English. It was developed by Gidropress Podolsk Company from the Russian Federation [2]. It is a pressurized water reactor (PWR); on this type of reactor, water is used for both as coolant and moderator [3].

PCTTRAN can be abbreviated as a personal computer transient analyzer; it is widely used to simulate nuclear power plant response. It was first introduced in 1985 by microsimulation technology [4]. This software is also available for various types of plants, including PWR, BWR, Westinghouse AP1000, Korean KSNP, etc. IAEA has selected PCTTRAN as a training software for its annual workshop. It is a user-friendly software, easy to use and understand, and it can be run faster than real-time [5]. All Faults considered in this paper a postulated initiating events for the design basis accidents (DBAs) [6].

2. Initial Condition and Boundary Conditions of VVER-1200 in PCTran

The initial steady state conditions of the plant are as follows:

Reactor Power: 100%

RC Pressure: 155 Bar

Core Average Temperature: 306.9 °C

Time in Life: EOC (End of Cycle)

SG Pressure: 70 Bar

Fig.1. Graphical user interface of PCTran VVER 1200

3. Faults

Malfunctions were introduced after 5 seconds of the initiation of the simulation. Malfunctions are LOCA in the cold leg with 75% failure fraction with 60% loss of AC power, tube rupture in generator A and B are 30% and 45% respectively, and one of the auxiliary pumps is malfunctioning.

Fig.2. Pressurizer, SG-A, SG-B, reactor core, reactor building water level (m)

The water levels of the reactor system, including the pressurizer, steam generator, core water, and reactor building, are depicted in Fig.2. The pressurizer level (%) drops after 5 seconds (Malfunctions Activated) as coolant leaks through the rupture, and the steam generator (SG) water level marginally drops. Internal leaks or pipe ruptures cause the water level in the reactor building to rise dramatically. The core water level in a nuclear reactor refers to the height of the coolant (usually water) covering the reactor core. It is crucial for maintaining safe operating conditions, as it ensures proper heat removal and prevents fuel overheating.

Fig.3. Peak fuel, RCS average, peak clad, RB temperature (°C)

Different temperatures, like reactor building, peak fuel, peak clad, and RCS average temperature, are plotted in fig.3 for 600 seconds. The Peak Fuel Temperature sharply increases to over 1600°C due to sudden loss of cooling, caused by LOCA or a loss of AC power. This is due to the heat generated by the nuclear fuel, which cannot be adequately removed. After the peak, the temperature decreases sharply as emergency cooling systems (ECCS) or passive safety systems activate to stabilize the core.

The cladding temperature rises significantly during the fault, likely due to heat transfer from the overheated fuel and insufficient coolant flow. Once cooling systems are restored, the cladding temperature decreases and stabilizes, showing that the system is regaining control. The RCS temperature slightly rises due to reduced heat removal capacity during the fault scenario. After initial adjustments, the RCS temperature stabilizes at a manageable level, reflecting restored heat removal processes. The RB temperature rises moderately, likely due to steam or hot coolant leakage into the containment.

Fig.4. Reactivity of soluble boron, modifier temperature, fuel doppler

LOCA results in rapid loss of reactor coolant, leading to fuel temperature increase. Doppler reactivity (gray line) quickly rises as fuel heats up. Temperature fluctuations impact reactivity, reflected in the orange curve.

Fig.5. Departure from nuclear boiling ratio

The Departure from Nucleate Boiling Ratio (DNBR) measures the safety margin between the actual heat flux in the reactor core and the critical heat flux at which coolant transitions from efficient nucleate boiling to unstable film boiling. After a rapid increase in fuel burnup inside the reactor, the core becomes unstable, and then the core materials melt down due to the increasing heat flux process.

- DNBR > 1: Safe operation
- DNBR ≤ 1: Dangerous situation

LOCA leads to a rapid loss of coolant, reducing heat removal from the core. Initially, DNBR would drop due to increased fuel temperature, but quickly rises and stabilizes. This can

happen either because emergency cooling systems are compensating or power is restored, allowing normal heat transfer to resume.

Fig.6. RCS Leak Mass Flow Rate

Flow of Reactor coolant system (RCS) coolant flow suddenly rises 684 kg/s at T=5s, then suddenly starts to fall. Due to tube rupture, at T=10 s the RCS pressure decreased below the threshold set point and then the turbine load power declined to zero instantly, with this, the core thermal power and nuclear flux power also decreased to a great extent.

Fig. 7. Power of Core thermal, nuclear flux, Turbine load (%).

It is observed from the simulation that the reactor trip occurs at 10 seconds due to the rapid depressurization of the RCS. Due to the decay heat of the reactor core, the Core Thermal Power and Nuclear Flux remain approximately 2% during the simulation.

Loss of cooling flow forces a reactor shutdown to avoid overheating. Tube rupture causes a heat transfer imbalance, without AC power, reactor cooling, and turbine generators failing. LOCA triggers an automatic reactor shutdown (SCRAM) to prevent overheating. Core thermal power, nuclear flux, and turbine load all rapidly decrease as the reactor shuts down.

4. CONCLUSION

The VVER-1200 reactor's excellent safety features are demonstrated by the transient study conducted under fault conditions. The automated safety mechanisms of the reactor successfully stabilized the core parameters despite the LOCA, loss of AC power, tube ruptures, and auxiliary pump failure. Severe damage was avoided by using emergency cooling (ECCS) and SCRAM shutdown to reduce reactivity changes, pressure decreases, and rising fuel temperatures. The DNBR recovery confirmed safe heat transfer restoration. These findings demonstrate the robustness of the VVER-1200 and reinforce the need for continuous safety enhancements in nuclear power plants.

5. REFERENCES

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